

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

GREENGAGE interoperable tools for urban analytics data to policy workflow lifecycle 2

Work Package 4, Deliverable D4.4

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

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List of Acronyms

CO	Citizen Observatory
CS	Citizen Science
EO	Earth Observation

Glossary

Citizen Science campaign	A Citizen Science (CS) Campaign comprises a period when a group of Citizen Observers with a shared mission and hypothesis gather data at different places and regularly get together to analyse together the correlation of their collected data with other external data sources to validate such hypothesis
Citizen Observatory	Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. In GREENGAGE, COs oversee running CS campaigns to gain evidence for policy making. Notice that a Citizen Science (CS) Campaign comprises a period when a group of Citizen Observers with a shared mission and hypothesis gather data at different places and regularly get together to analyse together the correlation of their collected data with other external data sources to validate such hypothesis
GREEN Engine	GREENGAGE's dedicated technological platform leveraging GREEN Infrastructure to enable GREENGAGE CO activities.
GREENGAGE CO coordinators	Coordinators of COs are those participants that deliver the Innovation Action (IA). To demonstrate innovation, these coordinators must ensure that the urban challenges are communicated as defined by top-down perspectives (e.g., EU policies, academic expertise). Therefore, they regulate their co-examination by providing methodologies, communication platforms, templates, checklists, surveys, consent forms and frameworks for specification.
Participants of COs	In GREENGAGE, we are applying a broader understanding of participants as human and non-human actors. Building on feminist perspectives in Science and Technology Studies, we understand that humans do not drive change by themselves but through their interactions with technologies and discourses (Clarke et al. 2018, p. 70). A broader understanding of participants is useful for addressing the existing power relations that shape open innovation ecosystems.
Pilot Owner	The city or authority responsible for the implementation of a particular GREENGAGE innovation pilot.
Thematic Co-Explorations	A Thematic Co-Explorations involves a group of people that combines already available datasets (Open Data, Copernicus) with those datasets that citizenry can contribute with. The idea is that heterogenous datasets are combined and correlated to give place to indicators and visualisations that are widely understandable by laypeople. Besides, the conclusions or insights driven by each pilot will be mapped into storylines, i.e., narrative, and visual communication to raise awareness about the issues associated to Green Deal and possible solutions that as society we can tackle.

Executive summary (publishable)

This document describes the interoperability of tools for urban analytics data to policy, provided by GREENGAGE consortium members, to support the whole data value chain in the project's Citizen Observatories. It depicts how different sensors (wearables) and portable crowd sourced air quality and environmental variables' sensors (e.g., from HOPU/Libelium/Moondial), as well as street-view imaging devices from MindEarth and the mobile GREENGAGE app (Digital Sunray/SushiDev, integrated with AIT's MODE library) are leveraged, and the corresponding provided information is properly (pre-) processed and integrated into the GREEN Engine. This document is the follow-up document to D4.3 which described the planned steps of using interoperable tools for urban analytics. It shows the complete workflow of an actual crowd sourcing campaign in Bilbao with the GREEN Engine, following the vocabularies and standard API defined in task T4.1.

Related documents

GREENGAGE Deliverable D4.2 - GREEN Engine and Manual 2

GREENGAGE Deliverable D4.3 - GREENGAGE interoperable tools for urban analytics data to policy workflow lifecycle 1

Completion of a Citizen Science Loop with GREENGAGE - <https://greengage-project.github.io/Documentation/CS-loop-GREENGAGE/>

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aims to promote innovative governance processes, and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project will leverage citizens' participation and equip them with innovative digital solutions that will transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, citizens will be inspired to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The aim is to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This will be facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories will be a place where pilot cities will co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up process with top-down perspectives. This will provide the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aims to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The envisioned citizens observatory campaigns will be deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano and Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aim to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which will complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2 Object of the Deliverable

This report is an attachment to the Demonstrator (deliverable D4.4, Task 4.2, see figure below) which describes the interoperability of GREENGAGE’s tools. An actual workflow of this demonstrator was put into action by the consortium and is outlined in section 0 of this document. Using this established “cookbook” allows pilots to follow similar workflows themselves using the support of COs. Following is the actual Task description which this deliverable is based on.

Deliverable D4.4 – GREENGAGE interoperable tools for urban analytics data to policy workflow lifecycle 2

Deliverable Number	D4.4	Lead Beneficiary	1. AIT
Deliverable Name	GREENGAGE interoperable tools for urban analytics data to policy workflow lifecycle 2		
Type	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Due Date (month)	30	Work Package No	WP4

Description
This deliverable covers T4.2 and will highlight lessons learned.

Task 4.2 GREENGAGE interoperable toolbox for scalable and flexible Citizen Observatories (Duration: M1–M30) [AIT, DEUSTO, GISAT, VRVis, Sushi Dev, DSR, BUAS, MindEarth, HOPU].

This task will deliver a range of tools provided by consortium members to support the whole data value chain in Citizen Observations (see concept in Figure 1). For Data Capture, e.g., sensors (wearables) from Moondial and portable crowd air quality and environmental variables sensors from HOPU, street-view imaging devices from MindEarth and mobile apps as the GREENGAGE app with MODE integration will be leveraged and corresponding information will be properly (pre-) processed and harmonizingly integrated into the GREEN Engine. Data quality and structure dashboards from VRVis and citizen contribution validation, accounting and rewarding DLT-based solutions (from DEUSTO & Sushi Dev) will support data curation process and again will be integrated into the GREEN Engine. Data harmonisation will be carried out based on the standard vocabularies approach of the Urban-TEP which currently allows it to manage EO imagery, statistics, surveying, and volunteered geographic information. If needed, adaptors for new data sources will be created for the intended GREEN Engine. Besides, Data Analytics will be supported by CO₂ analytics engine (AIT); Mobility footprint monitoring (AIT, BUAS) or AI models of environmental conditions that impact public health (HOPU). These tools range from TRL 4-8. These tools will be tailored to CO experiments needs in the Pilot cities in T4.4. Additionally, based on the requirements driven in the task 2.5, some new features or CO tools will be provided or implemented by adapting existing open-source tools. We will start early and continue during piloting phase through T4.4. Through the CO Academy front-end provided by T4.3 users will easily access the resulting reusable GREENGAGE tools documentation, open-source code and deployment instructions facilitated by module bundling as Docker containers. T4.2 will implement the adaptor and connector of the digital twin of Noord-Brabant with the GREEN Engine, following the vocabularies and standard API defined in T4.1. The work on Digital Twin Noord Brabant is embedded in all the tasks of this work package. One of the key ambitions for the North Brabant is to ensure that proper methods and mechanisms of citizen-crowdsourced data inclusion into the digital twin are well established. Within WP4 the configuration of the data value chains for the North Brabant Digital Twin, combining authoritative data with crowdsourced data, will be organised (T4.1).

3 Introduction

Project GREENGAGE aims to enable citizens to do so called **thematic co-explorations** within Citizen Observatories. Multiple steps are needed to achieve this goal, and GREENGAGE starts from the overall Citizen Science concept, co-creating scientific hypotheses with citizens which need to be validated through the following steps and potentially ending, as a final goal of GREENGAGE, in a change in policymaking and planning within GREENGAGE’s pilots (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Citizen Science loop

A Citizen Science loop consists of six distinctive steps, namely:

1. *Problem identification* – recognizing research questions or societal challenges suitable for public engagement
2. *Campaign design* – co-selecting and co-designing participatory protocols, data collection methodologies, and toolkits for citizens’ engagement
3. *Data crowdsourcing* – enabling citizen scientists to gather good quality observations via digital applications, sensors, and surveys, through data crowdsourcing activities
4. *Data analysis & interpretation* – employing AI-driven tools for insight extraction and thus making humanly meaningful the data modelled
5. *Feedback & collective learning* – validating findings with humans and providing participants with actionable feedback; and
6. *Action & impact* - informing policies, creating solutions, and refining methodologies for future CS campaigns exploring similar or complementary thematic co-explorations.

This document will focus mainly on steps 3 and 4 and describe the tools used to gather and analyse the data and how the tools work together.

4 The interoperable toolbox

4.1 Overview of the tools

GREENGAGE's so called GREEN Engine combines many different tools to acquire data which are needed for urban analytics within the project's Citizen Observatories (COs):

- **Realtime Mapping & Image Analysis (MindView from MindEarth)** is installed as an app and collects and uploads geo-tagged street-level photos taken by its users which are then analysed to gather high-level information about the places under investigation:
 - Number of people, including socio-demographics like age, gender.
 - Information on streets (e.g., layout, pavement quality, presence of sidewalks, traffic signs, parking space utilization ...)
- **Dashcam-based Road Defects Detection (UWE):** The image analysis work has been successfully extended to dashcam footage, aiming to spot a wide range of roadway defects for the Turano pilot—including potholes, surface cracks, faded road markings, and vandalised road signs. As part of the initial training phase, we deployed CVAT to label representative frames from the dashcam videos. Further, we integrated Segment Anything Model (SAM) model inside CVAT to speed up and accelerate the annotation process. An AI model is currently under development, and an early prototype already demonstrates promising results, offering side-by-side visual analysis of identified defects. The next release will output structured JSON files detailing all roadway defects and respective metadata, enabling research and development for downstream urban use cases. This is an exciting and evolving area of work, with ongoing iterations to increase accuracy, usability, and scalability.
- **Portable Devices for environmental data capture (HOPU) or of-the-shelf wearables like Atmotube¹ etc.** measure concentrations, such as H₂S, NH₃, VOC's NO, NO₂, SO₂, CO and O₃ in the air. In addition, they can measure other parameters, such as particulate matter for PM1, PM2.5 and PM10.
- The **Collaborative Environment (CE)** offers a digital environment that facilitates co-production processes between Public Administrations, private stakeholders and citizens and promotes the re-use of software and knowledge assets for the delivery of public services and thematic co-explorations. It deals with community and process management of a thematic co-exploration.
- **VISAT and Urban Thematic Exploitation Platform (UTEP) (GISAT)** provide an open-source web-based analytical framework in form of a platform which allows to represent metrics and layers of information over geographical and satellite representations. The portal is connected to distributed high-level computing clusters and clouds, providing key functionalities for high-performance data access, analysis and visualization.
- **MODE (AIT)** software technology which uses smartphones to automatically track the distances travelled and transport modes used. It is a microservice which can be integrated into third party apps.
- **Data Quality and Structure Dashboard (VRVis)** offers intelligent visual analytics dashboards for an in-depth structural analysis and quality check of time-series data. For instance, we may inspect the completeness of time-series data (i.e., detection of missing values and missing periods), the accuracy of time-series data (i.e., detection of duplicate timestamps), or carry out an anomaly detection (i.e., detection of outliers or unusual sequences of identical values).
- **GREENGAGE app (Digitalsunray, SushiDev)** is an adaptation of the earlier HotCity app (which was a blockchain solution for identifying spatial infrastructure in cities). Key idea behind the GREENGAGE app is to provide a universal tool to help engage Citizen Observatories in the research within the scope of the project through completion of Pilot-defined tasks in a comprehensible and gamified manner.

¹ <https://atmotube.com/atmotube-pro>

- **Sentiment analysis (UWE):** Using Large Language Models (LLMs) - Flan-T5, sentiment analysis is performed on transcripts from videos, interviews, and written texts from citizens. Inputs are processed by the LLM to detect emotional tone and classified with a binary label (1 for positive sentiment and 0 for negative). This approach enables rapid assessment of overall emotional trends, helping to quickly understand the prevailing mood or attitude expressed across large volumes of collected data. The models used are run locally to avoid sharing information with third party software.
- **Summarisation and thematic analysis (UWE):** As part of the Bristol pilot, a text summarisation service leveraging LLaMA 3 is being developed to summarise content from qualitative comments submitted by citizens through the EBLN platform. This tool is designed to help the pilot owner and other stakeholders quickly grasp key themes and sentiments from large volumes of textual survey data. To support experimentation and broader usability, a stream lit web application has been created, enabling users to upload their own datasets and explore summarisation across various contextual settings. Initial evaluations by domain experts have shown that summarisation quality can vary depending on the context provided, an insight that is guiding further refinement. Building on this foundation, the work is now being extended to include thematic summarisation, aiming to group and highlight recurring topics and concerns more effectively. This evolving capability holds strong potential for enhancing civic engagement analysis and decision-making.

For a full documentation of the tools please visit <https://greengage-project.github.io/Documentation/> and deliverable *D4.2 GREEN Engine and manual 2*.

4.2 Data exchange between the tools

Full documentation of the interoperability with other tools is described in detail in deliverable *D4.5 Experiment and monitoring system and manual 1* and will not be duplicated here. This document focuses how these interoperable tools are used for urban analytics.

5 Workflow of using the interoperable toolbox for urban analytics

This section showcases the process, tools and results obtained when applying the GREENGAGE CO-enabling approach to a real use-case, namely, “*reflection on the suitability and air quality of important points of interest (POIs) within the campus of the University of Deusto in Bilbao, Spain*”. The following subsections describe the different steps completed towards fulfilling the citizen science loop for this thematic co-exploration with a focus on the tools and interactions between them.

5.1 Problem Identification and Campaign Design

To facilitate the coordination and the execution of this co-creation process, a new one was defined in the Collaborative Environment as shown in the following Figure 3.

Figure 3: A new process was defined in the Collaborative Environment

This makes it easier to coordinate the first two steps of the co-creation process (see Figure 2) – CS campaign specification and the design of the crowdsourcing campaign. With the research questions defined, the citizen observatory was created in the backend (Figure 4).

Figure 4: GREENGAGE Backend for setting up citizen observatories

5.2 Data crowdsourcing

On Friday 14 March 2025, from 11:30am to 12:30pm CET, a crowdsourcing campaign was executed, where 10 people took part. Notice that participants were requested to complete the following actions before starting the crowdsourcing campaign:

1. They had to log into <https://me.greengage-project.eu/> and complete a sociodemographic form as the one shown in Figure 5. Notice that this form requires that each participant specifies their role in the thematic co-exploration, gender, age range, work status, education level and so on. Besides –and very importantly– participants must accept a consent form at the bottom of this page by means of which GREENGAGE is allowed to process their supplied data and aggregate with other participants' sociodemographic data, still preserving the privacy of participants at all times. Only, after they have completed this form, users are allowed to log into the GREENGAGE app devised to capture data.

The screenshot shows a registration form on a green background. At the top right, there is a 'Select Language' dropdown. Below it is a circular profile picture placeholder with a 'Select and Upload Photo' button. The user's name is 'Diego Lopez de Ipiña Gonzalez de Artaza' with a unique ID 'c6db5214-d819-4e4b-b294-d618287f724b' and email 'dipiña@cleusto.es'. The form includes a 'Welcome to GREENGAGE!' message and a detailed consent text. The role selection is 'Core team member - organizer and knowledge leader of a thematic co-exploration'. Location is 'Bilbao', gender is 'Male', education is 'PhD', digital knowledge is 'Advanced level', work status is 'Employed (private sector)', organization type is 'Non-profit organization', and age is '45-54 years - Late adulthood'. A consent checkbox is checked, and a 'Submit' button is at the bottom.

Figure 5: A new user for the Citizen Observatory was created

2. They had to complete a [PRE Impact evaluation questionnaire](#) as the one shown below. Its [PDF printout](#) showcases how participants in a CS campaign held within GREENGAGE are questioned

about environmental, political, scientific and social impact perception before they take part in a thematic co-exploration.

GREENGAGE - PRE Impact ex-ante Questionnaire (Citizen Observatory participants)

dipina@deusto.es [Switch accounts](#)
Not shared

* Indicates required question

Environmental Issues and concerns

2.1 Listed below are statements about the relationship between humans and the environment. For each one, please indicate whether you strongly agree, mildly agree, and unsure, mildly disagree or strongly disagree with it.

	Strongly disagree	Mildly disagree	Unsure	Mildly agree	Strongly agree
We are approaching the limit of the number of people the earth can support	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Humans have the right to modify the natural environment to suit their needs	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When humans interfere with nature, it often produces disastrous consequences	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Human ingenuity/intelligence will ensure that we do NOT make the earth unliveable	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Humans are severely abusing the environment	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure 6: PRE-Impact evaluation questionnaire

- They had to download and install the GREENGAGE app from either [Android's Google play store](#) or [Apple's app store](#) on their smartphones. Notice that the GREENGAGE app also allows users to register as done in step 1, if they do not have credentials, so that they get access to the app easily. After, these preparation activities, participants were ready to launch the GREENGAGE app, as shown below, and use it to collect data.

Figure 7: GREENGAGE App

- Right after concluding the crowdsourcing campaign, participants were also requested to complete a [POST Impact evaluation questionnaire](#) as the one shown below. Its [PDF](#)

[printout](#) showcases how participants in a CS campaign held within GREENGAGE are questioned about environmental, political, scientific and social impact perception after they take part in a thematic co-exploration.

Figure 8: POST-Impact evaluation questionnaire

The crowdsourced campaign data was collected by applying an [ETL process](#). Whilst the PRE and POST impact and satisfaction questionnaires are hosted in Google Forms, the GREENGAGE app's collected data is hosted on an [Apollo Server](#) which exhibits a [GraphQL](#) API. This API allows clients (such as mobile apps or web frontends) to efficiently query and interact with campaign data. This interface was used to retrieve all data crowdsourced associated to the POIs and spots generated in the above-described thematic co-exploration's crowdsourcing campaign.

Through the Apollo Server front-end, shown below, details in JSON about tasks performed in the crowdsourcing campaign are retrieved by means of a GraphQL query. Notice that GraphQL is a modern API query language and runtime that allows clients to request precisely the data they need in a single request, unlike RESTful APIs which rely on multiple endpoints and fixed data structures, often leading to over-fetching or under-fetching of data.

Figure 9: GraphQL query of GREENGAGE Observatory data

The ETL process corresponding to the crowdsourcing campaign was implemented as a Python script utilizing asynchronous programming patterns to efficiently extract, transform, and load GREENGAGE app's data. For data extraction, the script interfaces with GREENGAGE app's GraphQL API endpoint to retrieve mission data, including various mission types (e.g. SURVEY, WALK or DATASET). Additional observatory-related data is collected to provide geographical context for each mission during transform stage of the process. Finally, the script also interfaces with a [Keycloak-based authentication service customized for GREENGAGE](#), which allows extracting participants' socioeconomic user data. Internally, this extension of KeyCloak has a [PostgreSQL database](#) which can be queried through SQL. This service enables anonymization while preserving demographic information.

During transformation, mission data is processed according to type-specific rules. For example, a SURVEY type task requires additional API calls to retrieve associated quantitative survey values, or GEOTRACKING type mission requires additional API call to retrieve associated GeoJSON object. The transformation phase maps tasks to observatory information, enriches records with anonymized user demographic data, and converts all data to a standardized CSV format with appropriate fields for analysis. This step is crucial because [Apache Druid](#), the real-time analytics database used in the loading phase, requires data to be ingested in a structured format. The [deployment of Druid performed for GREENGAGE](#) (see its [documentation](#)) stores data internally in a columnar format, which optimizes it for fast aggregations and queries.

Finally, the load phase utilizes [Apache Druid's ingestion API](#) to load the transformed data. The script generates a comprehensive ingestion specification defining data types, dimensions, and granularity settings to optimize subsequent analytical queries. Once ingested, the data becomes immediately queryable through Druid's SQL API, which enables seamless integration with visualization platforms like Apache Superset and other analytics tools.

Notice that three ETL processes were set up to extract, transform and load data from:

1. Photos gathered through task 2 (see [crowdsourcing campaign's spec](#))
2. Survey answers associated to the different users and POIs where surveys were responded through task 1 (see [crowdsourcing campaign's spec](#))
3. Sociodemographic data completed by participants when they signed up to take part in the observatory, by means of the <https://me.greengage-project.eu> page (Figure 5). As result of these ETL processes, data was stored in the Apache Druid infrastructure, which is the storage solution chosen within the GREEN Engine.

Time	mission_id	mission_topic	mission_type	mission_title	mission_description	mission_latitude	mission_longitude	city_name	city_id	poi_id
2025-03-12T15:11:38.000Z	9e6a4320-02ee-4c95-b2	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 3 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2716301	-2.9402689		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e69eaab
2025-03-12T15:11:38.000Z	9e6a4320-02ee-4c95-b2	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 3 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2716301	-2.9402689		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e69eaab
2025-03-12T15:11:38.000Z	9e6a4320-02ee-4c95-b2	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 3 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2716301	-2.9402689		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e69eaab
2025-03-12T15:11:38.000Z	9e6a4320-02ee-4c95-b2	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 3 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2716301	-2.9402689		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e69eaab
2025-03-12T15:11:38.000Z	9e6a4320-02ee-4c95-b2	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 3 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2716301	-2.9402689		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e69eaab
2025-03-12T15:26:49.000Z	9e6a4886-4ee6-4762-8e	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 4 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2711572	-2.9402953		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e6a475d
2025-03-12T15:26:49.000Z	9e6a4886-4ee6-4762-8e	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 4 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2711572	-2.9402953		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e6a475d
2025-03-12T15:26:49.000Z	9e6a4886-4ee6-4762-8e	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 4 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2711572	-2.9402953		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e6a475d
2025-03-12T15:26:49.000Z	9e6a4886-4ee6-4762-8e	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 4 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2711572	-2.9402953		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e6a475d
2025-03-12T15:26:49.000Z	9e6a4886-4ee6-4762-8e	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 4 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2711572	-2.9402953		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e6a475d
2025-03-12T15:26:49.000Z	9e6a4886-4ee6-4762-8e	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 4 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2711572	-2.9402953		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e6a475d
2025-03-12T15:26:49.000Z	9e6a4886-4ee6-4762-8e	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 4 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2711572	-2.9402953		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e6a475d
2025-03-12T15:26:49.000Z	9e6a4886-4ee6-4762-8e	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 4 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2711572	-2.9402953		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e6a475d
2025-03-12T15:26:49.000Z	9e6a4886-4ee6-4762-8e	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 4 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2711572	-2.9402953		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e6a475d
2025-03-12T15:26:49.000Z	9e6a4886-4ee6-4762-8e	AIR_QUALITY	SURVEY	Go to POI 4 at DEUSTO	Please go to this Point o 43.2711572	-2.9402953		Bilbao (Air Quality on C)	9e685bfe-c5d5-4d1f-87f	9e6a475d

Figure 10: Apache Druid showing raw data gathered by COs

During the campaign the following number of measurements were gathered:

- 10 people completed a sociodemographic questionnaire which granted them access to the GREENGAGE app after a consent form was signed.
- 10 people also completed the PRE Impact evaluation questionnaire, as part of the [ex-ante and ex-post evaluation approach](#) adopted by the project.
- 10 people completed the POST Impact evaluation questionnaire
- 21 photos by the 10 participants were gathered at spots near the 4 POIs, where potential issues were identified.
- 90 answers to the 3-question survey associated to each of the 4 POIs defined in the campaign were gathered.
- 180 air quality measurements were gathered by the 4 Atmotube devices carried by participants (39 PM2.5 measurements).

5.3 Data Analysis and Interpretation

Once the data had been ingested into Druid, an overview of the collected Atmotube air quality time series data could be quickly assessed using the Data Quality Dashboard. In just two steps—selecting the dataset of interest ("deusto_campaign_ATMOTUBE_data") and the measured value field ("PM2.5")—it could be confirmed that hourly aggregated air quality data is available for the desired timeframe (Friday 14 March 2025, from 11:30am to 12:30pm CET).

Figure 11 presents an overview of the dashboard, where the presence of PM2.5 data records within the specified timeframe can be verified across multiple panels: the Temporal Distribution panel (via the calendar heatmap in the bottom left), the Time Series Analysis panel (via the line chart in the bottom right), and the Data Table panel (top right).

Figure 11: Initial overview of air quality data in the Data Quality Dashboard collected during the campaign

Upon a more in-depth inspection of the raw, unaggregated entries from all devices, it appears that none of the devices recorded any noticeable outlier values during this period (see Figure 12). As such, there is no need to exclude specific measurement records, devices, or apply any numeric value thresholds in the subsequent analytical steps.

Figure 12: In-depth examination of recorded air quality data.

It is worth noting, however, that some records are missing location data. While this does not pose a problem for the current storytelling use case—since the precise measurement location is not critically important—it may warrant further investigation. This insight could prompt troubleshooting actions to prevent unintended loss of location data in the future, potentially caused by incorrect Atmotube app settings or phone configuration.

In the next step, with the help of the [Apache Superset tool](#), a range of visualizations were created at [GREENGAGE's deployment](#). A superset dashboard was created with Superset to analyse survey answers at each POI. Figure 14 shows the analysis of answers to the question “How do you rate air quality at POI?”. In the top left-hand side in the pie chart, we notice that participants’ perception was good or very good in 70% of the cases, i.e. for 7 out of the 10 participants that took part. The table below the pie chart shows the answers’ distribution out of the 4 categories (no answer for “bad” was received). For comparison, the PM2.5 concentration gathered by the 4 participants that also carried out an Atmotube device whilst they went around with the GREENGAGE app is shown at the bottom right side. During the crowdsourcing campaign’s time, the concentration of PM2.5 was in the range 1 to 7.8. Most studies indicate PM2.5 at or below 12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ is considered healthy with little to no risk from exposure. If the level goes to or above 35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during a 24-hour period, the air is considered unhealthy and can cause issues for people with existing breathing issues such as asthma. Hence, users’ perceptions regarding air quality match what the Atmotube devices reflected in their measurements.

Figure 13: Analysis of answers to question “How do you rate air quality at POI4?”

Additionally, results from all questions and all POIs were aggregated in other charts. For instance, Figure 14 (about survey results on the whole campus) depicts that in 55% of the cases, participants considered that the air quality at *all* the POIs, i.e. 4 points, was good or very good.

Figure 14: Survey results for the air quality of all POIs in the campus

5.4 Validation & Feedback

Step 5 and 6 of the full citizen science loop included validating findings with humans and providing participants with actionable feedback, informing policies, creating solutions, and refining methodologies for future CS campaigns, exploring similar or complementary thematic co-explorations. Analysing the data visualized in the Superset has allowed us to draw some further conclusions. There has been alignment between the perceptions regarding air quality and the actual measurements obtained through more reliable devices as Atmotube. This allows us to infer that even without the complexity of people needing to obtain/carry around the Atmotube sensors, the subjective point on the air quality can still be used to find hotspots of bad air quality.

Additional qualitative feedback from those visiting the POIs can be used to improve small annoyances on the campus. Participants took some pictures close to the POIs where they found something remarkable regarding the suitability or the air quality of the place (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Visual feedback provided by the citizen observers

Analysing the spots and the comments received in question 3 of survey 1, it was found that although generally the status of the campus is considered quite adequate, the fact that pedestrians and cars often share common spaces is troublesome for some.

To close the CS loop and contribute towards the positive transformation of Deusto's campus in Bilbao, the following internal and external tools were used for communication:

1. A [Discourse channel](#) was created through which participants could communicate with each other. Results were announced through this Discourse channel, and participants had the opportunity to comment on the generated visualizations and in the interpretations performed by all of them.
2. X and LinkedIn social media channels were used to summarize the thematic co-exploration completed main conclusions.
3. (Anonymised) datasets gathered from this thematic co-exploration were uploaded into [Zenodo community for GREENGAGE](#)

5.5 Reflection on Results of the Co-Exploration

A key part of the co-exploration process is the visual interpretation of data, which facilitates co-creation and meaningful dialogue between citizens and policymakers through evidence-based insights. This concept is currently under development and realized in the UrbanTEP/VISAT application (see design draft in Figure 16), developed by GISAT, which offers a user-friendly interface designed to help users explore data, understand project contexts, and engage with the challenges faced by pilot cities.

The data available in the application stems from data collection campaigns and stakeholder contributions, forming the basis for compelling narratives and data-driven stories. UrbanTEP/VISAT effectively translates these inputs into an interactive web application, making complex information accessible and engaging.

Each story not only includes stakeholder-provided data accessible to non-expert users, but also encourages expert users to explore the data further. Through integration with advanced tools like Apache Druid and Apache Superset, provided by the GREEN Engine, users can perform deeper analyses, visualize results, or download datasets for extended research and operational use.

Figure 16: Design draft of UrbanTEP / VISAT application currently under development

6 Summary, challenges and outlook

This document provides an overview on how the GREENGAGE tools were used interconnectedly to analyse urban data to be used in a policy workflow lifecycle. The main insight is that laypeople, after brief training, can follow the right protocol to gather good enough data to perform effective analysis or, at least, reflect on the results of data analysis' visualizations to trigger further investigations, possibly with professional/calibrated sensors at identified POIs. Still, the generation of visualizations with Superset or the aggregation and curation of data through ETL processes is complex, requires programming and data analysis skills and training. Nevertheless, interpretation of charts can be made accessible if some more expert people explain and discuss results with participants. Hence, continuous guidance and support for participants in CS observatories is critical to maintaining their interest across the whole thematic co-exploration's duration. Above all, several feedback loops are necessary to keep the community tuned after each of the steps necessary to complete the CS loop, e.g. through a Discourse channel.

References

GREENGAGE Deliverable D4.1 – GREEN Engine and manual 1

GREENGAGE Deliverable D4.2 – GREEN Engine and manual 2

GREENGAGE Deliverable D4.3 - GREENGAGE interoperable tools for urban analytics data to policy workflow lifecycle 1

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION